

ADVANCING AFRICAN'S DEVELOPMENT THROUGH GOOD GOVERNANCE: A CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS OF SELECTED HATE SPEECHES IN NIGERIA POLITICAL SPACE

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Abstract

Speeches are written with clear intents and purposes to inform, persuade, amuse, explain, or influence ideas. Politics in Nigeria, or perhaps all over the world often involves hate Speeches. Such speeches often aim at damaging the reputation or credibility of an individual or group in a bid to gain political power. This calls for concern in order to attain development and good governance in Africa, and particularly in Nigeria. This study analyses selected hate Speeches from different political dispensations and political players in Nigeria. The data for the study were sourced from the media (The print media, Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, etc.). The hate speeches selected and analysed cover the period of 2012 to 2023. The population of the study consists of Nigerians and international communities with participants cutting across different categories of people. Pragmatics forms the theoretical basis for the study. Analysis of the selected hate speeches will be guided by Bach and Harnish's intention and inference approach. The findings show that hate Speeches are prevalent in the Nigerian political space and are capable of disrupting the political system of the nation as well as hinder progress and development. The study recommends the need to put under control hate Speeches among politicians and political participants. This will help individuals to be conscious of their utterances and avoid statements that may incite hatred, and thus put an end to the menace of hate Speeches in the political affair of the nation.

Key words: Hate speech, Politics, Good governance, Development, Context, Pragmatics.

Introduction

The basic of human interaction is language as no normal being can exist in isolation. It is the medium through which ideas, feelings, thoughts are shared among people or members of same speech community. This is to say that language is central to human existence. The social framework of man depends largely on language. Its users think and act in it (Kekere-Ekun, 2006 P1). It is a formidable instrument of communication by which human experience is analysed (Martinet, 1970. P20).

Language is very crucial for human survival and existence because it is the most important and effective tool for communication. It is the bond that holds societies and nations together. The primacy of language cuts across all facets of human life, government, education, politics, health,

religion, e.t.c . Taiwo (2009. P92) observes that language conveys power. It moves people to exercise their franchise, debate and even revolt. Since this paper is on contextual analysis of selected hate speeches in Nigeria political space, we need to understand therefore, the relationship that exists between language and politics. Chilton (1998, P20) states that politics is the art of governance and power while language is the universal capacity of humans in all societies to communicate.

Politics is a struggle for power in order to put certain political, economic and social ideas into practice Bryran (2015, P23) politics is concerned with the power to make decisions, control resources, control other people's behaviour and at times control their values. In this process, language plays a crucial role for every political action is prepared accompanied, influenced and played by language.

Language plays an important role in politics because its main functions in different political situations is to enable politicians to form structurally stable social relationships. Fairclough (2006, P1) observes that it can "misrepresent as well as represent realities, it can weave visions and imaginations which can be implemented to change realities and in some cases improve human well-being, but it can also rhetorically obfuscate realities and construe them ideologically to serve in just power relations" in other words, language use in politics when put into action can yield democratic dividend or achieve the reserve.

The intrinsic link between language and politics has long been recognized, even in the days of Aristotle (1932) when he opines that man is more of a political animal than bees or any other gregarious animal and man is the only animal which she has endowed with the gift of speech". (Politics, I.11). Beard (2000. P.2) suggests that it is necessary to study the language of politics because it enables us to "understand how language is used by those who wish to gain power, those who wish to exercise power and those who wish to keep power. Several attempts have been made to define hate speech.

According to Mrabure (2016) hate speech is commonly used to describe any message that disparages a specific person or a group of people. Hate speech can be in the form of speech, gesture, behaviour, writing, or display. On the bases of this, politically motivated hate speech is generally an antecedent to election related provocation and violence in Nigeria. Essentially, such speeches rob others of their dignity. Therefore, United Nation (2016) highlighted that hate speech includes: a) all dissemination of ideas based on racial or ethnic superiority or hatred, by whatever means; (b) incitement to hatred, contempt or discrimination against members of a group on grounds of their race, colour, descent, or national or ethnic origin; (c) threats or incitement to violence against persons or groups on the grounds in (b) above; (d) expression of insults, ridicule or slander of persons or groups or justification of hatred, contempt or discrimination on the grounds in (b) above, when it clearly amounts to incitement to hatred or discrimination; and (e) participation in organizations and activities which promote and incite racial discrimination.

Hate speech to Kukah (2015), is any communication that denigrates a particular person or a group on the basis of race, colour, ethnicity, gender, disability, sexual orientation, nationality, religion, or other characteristics. It can be in the form of any speech, gesture or conduct, writing or display, and usually marks incitement, violence, or prejudices against an individual or a group. It is a speech that employs discriminatory epithets to insult and stigmatize others on the basis of their race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, or other forms of group membership (Adibe, 2015). In the Nigerian context, hate speech includes acts of insulting people for their religion, abusing people for their ethnic or linguistic affliction, and expressing contempt against people because of their place of origin (Umar, 2015. P.5).

To me as the researcher, hate speech is a deliberate malicious, unjustified and unstained effort to damage the reputation or the credibility of an individual. It is the slandering of a person, usually to destroy his/her public confidence. Hate speech is the act of lowering other individuals in a bit to ruin the character and acceptability of that individual. This destructive phenomenon has been a pandemic found everywhere in our society.

From the foregoing definitions, it suffices to align with the thought of a political scientist and media commentator, Adibe (2015) that hate speech is a catalyst for violence and that it is very doubtful if there would be hate-motivated violent attack anywhere without hate speech and the hatred that it purveys.

In the same vein, according to Neisser, (1994, P. 337), hate speech refers to “all communications (whether verbal, written, symbolic) that insult a racial, ethnic and political group, whether by suggesting that they are inferior in some respect or by indicating that they are despised or not welcome for any other reason”. On the other hand, Kayambazinthus and Moyo (2002) refer to hate speech as “war waged on others by means of words.” This understanding of hate speech is particularly true when it comes to hate speech on social media networks. Online hate speech is mainly characterized by the use of words and symbols.

According to Gagligardone et al (2014. 13-15) online hate speech is not essentially different from similar expressions found offline; however, there are some specific characteristics as well as challenges unique to online content and its regulation. They summarize these characteristics as permanence, itinerant, anonymity or pseudonym, and transnationality. On permanence, hate speech can remain online for a long period of time and in different formats across different platforms, and can be repeatedly linked. In this sense, the architecture of any particular platform influences how long topics ‘stay alive’. For instance, Twitter is built around the idea of trending topics, which may facilitate quick and wide dissemination of hateful messages; however, if topics are ignored, discussion rapidly fades. Facebook, on the other hand, provides the opportunity for long-lasting discussion threads. Notwithstanding, online hate speech content may particularly be itinerant, which means that even when it is removed from one platform, it may find expression elsewhere, possibly on the same platform under a different name or in different online spaces. If a website is shut down, it can quickly reopen using a web-hosting service with less stringent regulations or via reallocation to a country with laws imposing a higher threshold for hate speech. The itinerant nature of hate speech also means that poorly formulated thoughts that would not have found public expression and support in the past may now arrive on spaces where they can be visible to large audiences.

Very recently, researchers are beginning to show interest in hate speech as it is taking over our political and social media space. Attempts have been made by researchers to analyse hate speech in our society. One of these attempts was made by Bassey (2020) carried out a study on electoral campaign and hate speech in print media. His study focused on the use of hate speech before, during and after the 2015 general elections. The study did an analysis of the January, 19th 2015 advert on the Punch Newspaper. The research design adopted was content analysis. The paper discovered that the advertisement should not have been allowed because it promoted hate speech and was against the ethics of Nigeria Press Council. The study, therefore, concludes that the advertisement was inimical to democracy and against the ethics of journalism. However, Bassey’s study differs from the present one because while the study focused on hate speech in electoral campaigns in print media, the present study pays attention to hate speeches against President Muhammadu Buhari.

Bamigbola (2017) also did a critical discourse analysis of Gen. Muhammadu Buhari's Post-Election Speeches. The two speeches analysed were his acceptance speech as the president-elect on April 1, 2015 and his inaugural speech after his swearing-in on May 29, 2015. This study relying on Fairclough and Dijk's models for Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar examined the rhetorics in the language use of the speaker and the trend of the speeches. The findings of the study revealed that the use of language of the speaker centres on current happenings and pervading feelings in the society. The study also found that the speaker's propositions and views are based on his previous experiences as a Minister, a military Head of State and a long-term participant in the political arena of the nation.

Fiberesima in 2021 examined social media and hate speech with a view to looking at its implications for socio-political stability in Rivers State. Seven hundred (700) questionnaires were retrieved from the public to whom these questionnaires were distributed. Responses to questions were analysed and statistical results revealed a significant positive relationship between social media and hate speech. His findings revealed that those that propagate hate speech are usually elected officials, political parties, candidates for elective positions, opinion makers, and civil society officials.

Alkali and others carried out a study on audience perception of hate speech and foul language on social media in Nigeria. The aim of their research was to look at the moral and legal consequences the growing trend of hate speech and foul language on social media has on journalism and society as a whole. The paper concluded based on the findings that hate speech and foul language are prevalent on social media platforms in Nigeria and that there is adequate legal provisions to curb the phenomenon.

Theoretical Framework

Leech (1983:4) says pragmatics can be usefully defined as the "study of how utterances have meanings in situations." According to Kress (1985: 18) texts arising in specific social situations are constructed with specific purposes by one or more speakers or writers, and meanings find their expression in a text in concrete situations of social exchange. Frocking, Rodman and Hams (2007:199) assert that pragmatics is concerned with the interpretation of linguistic meaning in context. Two kinds of context are relevant. The first according to them is linguistic context – the discourse that precedes the phrase or sentence to be interpreted; the second is situational context – virtually everything non-linguistic in the environment of the speaker.

Pragmatics in essence deals with language in use. It deals basically with the meaning of utterance in context. Traugott and Pratt (1980:226) point out that "pragmatics deals with speaker's communicative competence, the knowledge which enables them to produce and understand utterance in relation to specific speech context." Thus, pragmatics is language in context from the point of view of the users, (primarily the speaker (or writer) and the hearer (or reader)). It involves choice of words (communication competence) and the constraints encountered in using language in social interaction (communicative competence) (Traugott & Pratt, 1980:226). Pragmatics goes further to account for the effects the use of language has on the participants in a communicative act. That is, it explains the relation between language as speech and language as a semantic system.

Pragmatics as the study of the way human beings use their language in communication, bases itself on a study of those premises and determines how they affect, and effectualise human language use. Hence, "pragmatics studies the use of language in human communication as determined by the conditions of society." (Mey, 2001:6). A pragmatic perspective will focus on the societal factors that make a certain language use more or less acceptable. (Mey, 2001:8).

Methodology

This study applies a qualitative descriptive design in order to describe the hate speech in Nigeria political space. Data gathering for this study involves two methods. The first part of the data used covers three different political dispensation that is (2011 to 2023). The second part of the data were collected through a twenty-item questionnaire used to sample from different individuals.

Hate Speech in Nigeria Political Space

The phenomenon of hate speech has become an important aspect of electioneering campaign today in Nigeria that numerous related conflicts are credited to it. The nation experience hate speeches during the 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 general elections, where politicians, religious figures public officers, citizens and ethnic nationalities express hate speech that increase the temp of the political environment derogatory speeches were made to label and demean opponents. Electioneering campaign in all these years in Nigeria democratization process were turned into a theatre of abhorrence utterances and disrespect for political opponents. Nigeria has divergent culture practice religious beliefs (Christianity, Islam, Traditional and others) with different backgrounds, education and social-political affiliations. It is unarguably that hate speech is dividing the nation because of political tussle among public figures and political party loyalist who struggle for political hegemony. This calls for much concern as responsible Nigerians.

The role of hate speech in political unrest and tension in Nigeria is really worrisome the pre and post electoral violence and hate speeches in 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 in the country are notable examples. Corroborating this, Akubor (2015) noted that the 2011 post-election violence in Nigeria shows that the hate speech played a major role in inciting people against one another. Also prior to the 2015, 2019 and 2023 general elections the country witnessed series of hate speeches by opposing political parties, especially among the major political parties the People Democratic Party (PDP), All Progressive Party (APC) and the Labour Party (LP).

Contextual Analysis of Selected Hate Speeches in Nigeria Political Space

1. *It must be Northerner or no Nigeria. If Goodluck Jonathan wins PDP's endorsement to contest the 2015 presidential election, there would be violence Dr Junaidu Mohammed 2nd Nov; 2010.*

This statement credited to Dr Junaidu Mohammed, National Coordinator of the coalition of Northern politician is an outright hate speech not only against Goodluck Jonathan but also against Nigerians. It is totally not acceptable for any politicians to be threaten others on the basis of religion and ethnic affiliation. Here, Junaidu threatened the peace, unity and co-existence of Nigeria if Buhari a Northerner does not win the general election

2. *God willing by 2015, something will happen they either conduct a free and fair election or they go a very disgraceful way. If what happened in 2011 should again happen in 2015, by the grace of God, the dog and the baboon would all be soaked in blood-Buhari 15th may, 2012.*

Muhammadu Buhari was the presidential candidate of All Progressive Congress in 2015. At one of the rallies organized by the party, he made this hate speech. This is quite unbecoming of a presidential candidate who means well for his people. Election should not be a do-or-die affair.

This statement created tension and fear in Nigeria. What is the need and relevance of an election, if there would be killing, destruction of properties and blood flow in the land? This threat has created the impression that the presence of Boko Haram in the North could be traced to statements such as this.

3. *There would be no peace not only in the Nigeria Delta, but everywhere if Goodluck Jonathan is not president by 2015, except God takes his life, which we do not pray for Majnhid Asari Dokubu, May, 5th 2013*

This uncouth and hate speech was made by the controversial Niger Delta agitators Asari Dokubu in a bid to show his support and loyalty to Jonathan, Dokubo expressed unreserved and totally unguided hate speech, threatening the peace of Nigeria.

4. *Nigerians, be warned! Nigerians... I have set before thee life and death. Therefore choose life that both thee and thy seed may liv will you allow history to repeat itself? Enough of state burials Nigeria vote wisely, vote Goodluck Jonathan (Ayo Fayose 2015)*

This advert goes beyond the person of Buhari. Death in this case means Islam, APC and the North. It is a hate generated against Islam, using quotation form the Bible. On the other hand, to choose Goodluck Jonathan , PDP, the South and Christianity is to choose life. In many parts of the world, and especially Nigeria which is potentially divided sectarian lines, such religious inference poses danger of provoking violence. It is designed to denigrate a person, a religion, a political party, a geographical entity that they represent death. The text is quoted from the book of Deuteronomy 30 verse 19: "I call heaven and earth to record this day against you, that I have set before You life and Death, blessing and cursing: therefore choose life, that both thou and thy seed may live." The Biblical quote is a provocation to adherents of other religions, especially since those he is attacking are Muslims. It also denigrates the sacredness of the Bible. It is using the sacred for the mundane, the holy for the dirty. The pronoun "I" is divine. It was God speaking. Fayose assumes the position of God instructing the mortal Nigerians not to stray to the North, to Islam, to APC and to Buhari because they symbolise death.

5. *Buhari is a mistake, Northerners can't vote someone like him again in 2023. (Northern Elders Forum)*

Buhari is of northern extraction. This translated to overwhelming support and unprecedented votes from the region. However, despite this support, he is considered to have failed the North and indeed Nigerians, hence he was given direct verbal confrontation. This statement credited to Northern Elder's forum fits into the hate speech classification because it evidently reveals the name of the person being attacked. This implies that the statement is a direct affront against the person of Muhammadu Buhari. Therefore, it is explicitly hate speech.

6. *The Buhari government is a calamity that befell the Nigeria state (Chris Agwn, AIT and Newspaper Review)*

Yes, this comment could be seen as coming from a frustrated and disappointed person. In the comment, Buhari's government has been reduced to calamity.

7. *Nowhere is safe, not the President's hometown nor his region, the President.*

This comment is a direct and explicit speech showing the speaker's negative attitude toward President Buhari. The extract represents judgment and accusation that Buhari is a failure. In this

case, President Buhari is also accused of not being able to protect Nigerians and in indeed his own people.

8. *Overfeeding gave us the energy to fight Jonathan, Now Buhari has caused us mass starvation. (Omokiri Reno, 2023)*

This comment is credited to Reno Omokri, one of the most-known critics of Buhari. Here, out of curiosity and outspokenness, he expresses his thoughts by comparing Jonathan's government and Buhari's in relation to the welfare of the citizens. His judgment of Buhari's government is negative and sentimental. It is an open confrontation full of hate speech.

9. *Bandits were created by Gen. Buhari to oust Jonathan (Credited to Nuhu Ribadu)*

This statement is coming from Nuhu Ribadu, former EFCC boss. This comment is a strong accusation leveled against President Buhari. The speaker shows a kind of dislikeness towards Buhari by altering this slanderous and venomous statement which sparked tension and uproar across the country. The seriousness of this, can be understood from the fact that many northern politicians and rulers are being pointed out as being responsible for the unrest in the North East and indeed Nigeria.

10. *Emi lo kan, emi lo kan*

Baba wen no well

E dey shout, emi lo kan

Hand dey shake

Leg dey shake

Baba wen no well

E dey shout, emi lo kan

Labour Party/PDP supporters. (2023)

There is no denying the fact that in 2023 general election, there was a build-up of tension along ethnic, regional, religious or party line, fostered by hate speeches in the country. One of such hate speeches is this song credited to Labour Party (LP) and Peoples Democratic Party supporters. This song was meant to humiliate the state of health of Ahmed Bola Tinubu, the presidential candidate of the All Progressive Congress in 2023 general elections. In order to discredit his candidacy.

Conclusion

Hate speech is a contemporary existential threat bedeviling nearly all countries. It has become very prevalent and turned to a very worrisome dimension in Nigeria politics. Rather than having campaign as instrument for expressing manifestos to the electorate on the ideas candidates want to share with the voters, hate speeches have taken over as an opportunity to indulge in defamation condemnation and attack of political oppositions and this can incite violence, undermine social cohesion and tolerance, and cause psychological, emotional and physical harm to those affected. Therefore calls for concern as responsible community members to take firm stance against it.

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